

Generation and Propagation of Distortion Products in the Gerbil's Mid-Turn Cochlea

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Abstract. We used OCT to record intracochlear DPs from the 2nd turn in the gerbil cochlea in the hope to determine the extent over which they contribute to DPOAEs. Since apical cochlear responses differ from basal one, we expect to see a much broader cochlear region (extended towards the base *re.* the f_2 tonotopic location) for low-frequency DPs. Measured at a fixed tonotopic location (BF \sim 2 kHz), we observed locally generated $2f_1 - f_2$ DPs (when f_2 was close to BF), forward propagating components (when $f_2 > \text{BF}$), and some evidence for reverse propagation ($f_2 < \text{BF}$ & wide f_2/f_1). For $2f_2 - f_1$, frequency response curves were independent of f_2/f_1 , and their phase indicated that they were a reverse propagating component. The latter suggests that these DPs contribute to the recorded DPOAEs (which were also found to be independent of f_2/f_1 .)

INTRODUCTION

The cochlea consists of a fluid filled tube that holds the sound-transducing, sensory epithelium (*i.e.*, the organ of Corti, ooC) along its length [1]. A place-frequency response gradient exists along this longitudinal axis such that high and low frequencies maximally excite the epithelium near the base and apex of the cochlea, respectively. Although appearing to be a single anatomical structure, the responses along the tonotopic axis are not the same: around three kHz a transition between "basal" and "apical" cochlear responses occurs [2, 3, 4, 5]. One of the transitioning responses is the group delay of $2f_1 - f_2$ distortion products (DPs) measured in the ear canal (distortion product otoacoustic emissions, DPOAEs) that arise when using a two-tone stimulus with frequencies f_1 and f_2 ($f_2 > f_1$). The basal-apical transition may originate from the reduced frequency selectivity and/or "breaking down" of scaling symmetry in the apical response. These changes potentially broaden both the cochlear region of DP-generation, and the extent from which these DP wavelets contribute to DPOAEs. Here, we used optical coherence tomography (OCT) to measure intracochlear DPs from "apical-like" locations in the (2nd turn of the) gerbil cochlea that had best frequencies (BF) of 2–2.5 kHz to study their generation and intracochlear propagation,

METHODS

All methods were similar to those described in [6, 7]. Briefly, recordings were from adult Mongolian gerbils (*M. unguiculatus*). Their care and use was in accordance with guidelines of, and approved by, the Institutional Animal Care and Use Committee (IACUC) of the VA Loma Linda Healthcare System. Animals were deeply anesthetized (ketamine/xylazine *i.p.* at 80/10 mg/kg, respectively) and kept at $\sim 38^\circ\text{C}$ using a heating pad (Harvard Apparatus) during the experiment. A ventrolateral approach surgically exposed the left cochlea, which itself was not compromised. The ipsilateral pinna and the cartilaginous ear canal were resected, and the tip of a microphone and transducer assembly (ER-10X, Etymotic Research) was sealed to the exposed ear canal for closed-field stimulus delivery. Animals were not allowed to recover from anesthesia and were euthanized by anesthetic overdose (Nembutal).

Images and vibratory responses from the ooC in the middle turn of the cochlea were recorded using a spectral domain OCT system (Thorlabs Telesto III TEL321C1 equipped with an LSM04 objective). Optical spectra were acquired at a rate of 24.4 ms^{-1} and converted into depth-resolved, axial information (A-line) using Fourier analysis. Multiple A-lines were obtained while scanning the OCT beam to create brightness images (B-scans).

For vibration measurements (M-scans), the phase information of the A-lines was used. With the OCT beam at a fixed position A-lines were recorded, while an acoustic stimulus was presented (RX6: Tucker Davies Technologies system III) to the ear. These stimuli were tone complexes with either 27 irregularly spaced frequency components, each one with a random starting phase ("zwijs" [8]) to obtain frequency response curves (FRC), or two tones for DP measurements. At each depth, vibratory responses at the stimulus frequencies were extracted from the recorded

FIGURE 1. (a) Brightness image (B-scan), obtained in the 2nd turn in the gerbil cochlea, orthogonal to the tonotopic axis. (b,c) Frequency response curves obtained at different SPL on the (b) basilar membrane and (c) in the outer hair cell/Deiters' cell region. The phase response curves were first normalized to the ME response, and then had an additional 0.5 ms removed. (d) Magnitude and phase vibmaps in response to a two-tone stimulus ($L_1 = L_2 = 60$ dB SPL, $f_2/f_1 = 1.25$, $f_2 = 2.13$ kHz = BF) for $2f_1 - f_2$, f_1 , f_2 and $2f_2 - f_1$. (e) Same as (d), but now with $f_2/f_1 = 1.45$.

signals using Fourier analysis. No artifact rejection was employed. Responses for each frequency component, and at each pixel, were only used in subsequent analysis when above the measurement noise floor.

The OCT system was controlled by custom software in C# (Visual Studio, Dev14), while stimulus generation, hardware synchronization and signal analysis were implemented in Matlab (MathWorks, R2018b).

RESULTS

Figure 1a shows a brightness image (B-scan), obtained in the 2nd turn in the gerbil cochlea, orthogonal to the tonotopic axis, in which the bony wall of the cochlea, the ooC, and the inner spiral ligament are easily discerned. Within the ooC, intensity variations also allow identification of the lateral compartment, the BM's pectinate zone, and the outer hair cell/Deiters cell region. A family of FRC, obtained at different sound pressure levels (SPL), from the BM (Fig. 1b) and OHC/DC region (Fig. 1c) showed that this tonotopic location had a best frequency (BF) of 2.13 kHz. These curves were as we described previously [6] with: (1) Larger OHC/DC magnitudes (*re.* BM) for sub-BF responses; (2) Compressive growth over a frequency range that extends well below BF for mid- and high-SPL; (3) "Hypercompression" for the highest SPL, especially when the stimulus frequency exceeds BF; (4) Phase-FRC characteristic of a traveling wave that abruptly slows down when approaching BF; and (5) Group delays that decreased with increasing SPL.

We recorded vibratory responses from multiple A-lines in this orthogonal cross section to create what we refer to as "vibmaps". These display either the magnitude or the phase of the responses to a single frequency component across the ooC. Figure 1d,e shows magnitude (*top row*) and phase (*bottom row*) vibmaps obtained in response to a two-tone stimulus for the two stimulus frequencies (f_1 , f_2) as well as the DPs at frequencies $2f_1 - f_2$ and $2f_2 - f_1$. In both panels $f_2 = \text{BF} = 2.13$ kHz, but the ratio f_2/f_1 differed.

Magnitudes, both at the stimulus and DP frequencies, varied considerably across the ooC, but the responses to the stimulus tones always exceeded those at the DP frequencies when $f_2 = \text{BF}$. As we will show, this scenario changed when $2f_1 - f_2 = \text{BF}$ (e.g., Fig. 3). The phase was variegated, both within and across vibmaps, although the latter variation would largely disappear when the frequency-dependent phase characteristics of the traveling wave are taken into account [6]. The within-map variation indicates that ooC motion was not "as one", but that different (sub-)structures

FIGURE 2. Phase vibmaps for (a) $2f_1 - f_2$ and (b) $2f_2 - f_1$ that were normalized to the phase of the stimulus tones on a pixel-by-pixel basis. (c) "Expected" difference ($2f_1 - f_2 - 2f_2 - f_1$) of the DP magnitudes as calculated from the recorded stimulus tone magnitudes (see text). (d) This "observed" DP magnitude difference in the recorded responses.

FIGURE 3. (a) Magnitude and phase vibmaps in response to a two-tone stimulus ($L_1 = L_2 = 60$ dB SPL, $f_2/f_1 = 1.25$, $2f_1 - f_2 = 2.13$ kHz=BF) for $2f_1 - f_2$, f_1 , f_2 and $2f_2 - f_1$. The third row of vibmaps repeats the phase-vibmaps, to the phase of the stimulus tones (see main text). (b) Same as (a), but now with $f_2/f_1 = 1.45$.

moved in different directions, warping the internals (and area? see [9]) of the ooC. Note how even within the OHC/DC region phase was far from constant. For example, the third-row OHC moved out-of-phase *re.* rows one and two. This differs from recorded OHC phase differences in the base of the gerbil cochlea, where row one moved out-of-phase *re.* rows two and three, [10], although this could also arise from differences in the angle between the OCT beam and the OHC orientation.

If we assume that the DP responses arose from a nonlinearity at the recording location (*i.e.*, they are locally generated), it is expected that their phase is 0.5 cycle when normalized to the phases of the stimulus tones (*re.* $2\phi_1 - \phi_2$ and $2\phi_2 - \phi_1$), and their amplitude is proportional to the stimulus amplitudes ($\propto 2L_1 + L_2$ and $2L_2 + L_1$) for $2f_1 - f_2$ and $2f_2 - f_1$, respectively. Figure 2a,b show these normalized phase maps for the data from Fig 1. For $2f_1 - f_2$ at $f_2/f_1 = 1.25$, the normalized phase was indeed close to 0.5 cycle, a strong indication that the recorded DPs originated from nonlinear interaction of the stimulus tones at this tonotopic location. The same held for $2f_2 - f_1$ throughout most of the ooC, except on the BM, where the phase-vibmap had a different hue (Fig. 2b, *top*). With $f_2/f_1 = 1.45$, the "deviating" (*i.e.*, not at 0.5 cycle) BM phase also appeared for $2f_1 - f_2$, while it became more pronounced for $2f_2 - f_1$. This suggests that these BM vibrations were not evoked by locally generated, but by traveling DPs: for $2f_1 - f_2$, the DP presumably originated more apically as a "reflection-DP" from its own BF location, while for $2f_2 - f_1$ the measured DP component originated from its own, more basally located tonotopic site. Why this latter component travelled towards the apex was likely due to the relatively shallow high-frequency slopes of the FRC. Some evidence for local and propagating DPs was seen in the amplitude response. Using the recorded amplitudes to the stimulus tones, we calculated the expected amplitude difference between $2f_1 - f_2$ and $2f_2 - f_1$ (Fig. 2c). Due to the shallow tuning, f_1 and f_2 response amplitudes were similar, thus creating similar $2f_1 - f_2$ and $2f_2 - f_1$ DPs. Therefore, the "expected" DP amplitude difference is close to 0 dB. Apart from a difference in absolute Δ DP, the pattern in the map with the observed magnitude differences (Fig. 2d) is comparable, except along the BM. Here, the $2f_2 - f_1$ DP exceeds its "expected" amplitude, again indicating that its origin is not at the recording site.

Forward propagation DPs are more dominant when $2f_1 - f_2 = \text{BF} = 2.13$ kHz. With $f_2/f_1 = 1.25$ (Fig. 3a), normalized $2f_1 - f_2$ phase significantly deviated from 0.5 cycle throughout the entire ooC, again indicating that recorded response

FIGURE 4. Amplitude and phase (normalized to f_1, f_2 phase) of responses in the **(a)** OHC/DC region and on the **(b)** BM, recorded with different f_2/f_1 (see legend). $L_1 = L_2 = 65$ dB SPL. Note how the normalized phase responses for the DP are only available for frequencies at which both stimulus tones gave a significant response.

did not originate here. With a larger $f_2/f_1 = 1.45$ (Fig. 3b), the stimulus tone responses were substantially reduced (f_1) or largely absent (f_2) because of their mismatch with BF. Despite this lack of "primary overlap", needed to generate local DPs, the $2f_1 - f_2$ remains robust. Although the relative phase vibmap could not be calculated (because the lack of ϕ_2 information), it is evident that this component must have arisen at a more basal cochlear location, and that it was captured by the OCT system after propagating to its own tonotopic site (=BF). With these stimuli, $2f_2 - f_1$ was too high (*re.* BF) and did not evoke much significant vibrations. This also precluded calculation of the expected and observed the DP magnitude ratios.

The vibmaps reveal details about the relative responses across the ooC, but they do not provide much frequency dependent information. We therefore supplemented them with BM and OHC/DC responses in which the stimulus tone pair was stepped over a range of frequencies while keeping their ratio constant (fixed- f_2/f_1 sweeps; Fig. 4). The OHC/DC responses to the stimulus tones were low-pass at these stimulus intensities ($L_1 = L_2 = 65$ dB SPL), while the BM responses retained some tuning (see also Figs. 1b,c). For DP at $2f_2 - f_1$, responses were largely independent on f_2/f_1 ratio, although the relatively low frequencies make it difficult to assess whether the different f_2/f_1 -curves maximally align when plotted versus f_2 or $2f_2 - f_1$. We did observe clear phase-vs-frequency gradients at all f_2/f_1 -ratios, where the slopes of the normalized phase curves were steeper on the BM than in the OHC/DC region. This suggests that the genesis of these DPs was more apical, from where they propagated to the recording site on their way to the ear canal to be (part of) the recorded DPOAE. We did observe (*not shown*) these low-frequency $2f_2 - f_1$ DPOAEs showed a similar independence on f_2/f_1 as the DPs.

For DP at $2f_1 - f_2$ the responses seemed more complex, but they can be explained by assuming that DPs were either locally generated and propagating components. This is easiest seen on the BM (Fig. 4b). A local component is recorded when f_2 is close to the recording site's BF (~ 2.5 kHz), which results in a local amplitude maximum, and a relative phase of 0.5 cycle. For $f_2 > 3$ kHz, the DP cannot be locally generated because (one of) the stimulus tones no longer evoke a response. Notwithstanding, significant $2f_1 - f_2$ responses were observed. These "high-frequency" DPs also exhibit a local maximum in each fixed- f_2/f_1 curve, but now these maxima align when plotted versus $2f_1 - f_2$. Moreover, the phase-vs-frequency curves all have a significant group delay at these frequencies that arises from the forward propagation of these DPs from the genesis to their own BF tonotopic site. For $f_2 < 2$ kHz (especially for $f_2/f_1 = 1.65$), the normalized phase suggest dominance of a reversely propagating component in the $2f_1 - f_2$ response. As far as we could assess, the responses in the OHC/DC region were qualitatively similar to those described for the BM.

CONCLUSION

We used OCT to record vibrations in response to two-tone stimuli to create vibmaps that detail the relative responses within the ooC at the stimulus and two DP frequencies. We observed that the DP and stimulus-tone vibmaps differed in their absolute amplitudes, but their "across-ooC" patterns were much alike, especially in their phase. The latter indicates that, from the cochlea's perspective, all frequency components are alike; it cannot differentiate between an internally generated DP and an externally presented tone. When normalized to stimulus-tone phase, the DP phase-vibmaps were relatively uniform throughout the ooC. Depending on the involved frequency (*-ies re.* BF), the BM responses sometimes showed a systematic phase deviation from the rest of the ooC-response. We interpret this as the

result from intracochlear DP propagation, where the recorded BM response is not to a locally generated DP, but to a component that had its genesis at a more basal/apical location. Evidence for DP propagation is also seen in these vibmaps when $2f_1 - f_2$ is at BF. Here, DP amplitudes exceeded f_1 , f_2 amplitudes and for $f_2/f_1 > 1.25$, $2f_1 - f_2$ DPs even occurred in the absence of significant f_1 , f_2 vibrations. This indicates that these DPs originated from basal source(-s).

To provide information on the frequency dependence of the response, we supplemented these vibmap recordings with fixed- f_2/f_1 sweeps in the OHC/DC region and on the BM. These showed that the $2f_2 - f_1$ DPs were independent of f_2/f_1 , and had significant (non-zero) group delays at all tested frequencies. The interpretation of the latter currently eludes us, as it suggests that this DP is always a non-local component, irrespective of the used stimulus frequencies. In addition, the associated group delays seem to suggest that these non-local components travel to the recording site within the OHC/DC region, after which they drive the BM with significant delay. For $2f_1 - f_2$, we observed both propagating (forward and reversly), as well as locally generated components, depending on the involved frequencies (f_1, f_2 and $2f_1 - f_2$). Since the recorded response is "winner-takes-all" (*i.e.*, the largest component dominates the response), the recording of either a local or a propagating component does not preclude the simultaneous existence of the other. Although our data indicate that the extent of $2f_1 - f_2$ generation is broad (in line with the extended range of nonlinear responses in the apical cochlea), it is difficult to assess which part of this extent "provides" DPs that contribute to the ear-canal DPOAE. It may therefore come as no surprise that we found only a (very) moderate correlation between $2f_1 - f_2$ DPs and DPOAEs in these experiments: the recorded DPs provide too much of a "myopic" view of the DPOAEs. Other stimulus protocols (*e.g.*, three-tone suppression experiments in which intracochlear DP sources are selectively removed via suppression) provide a better gauge for the intracochlear origin of DPOAE. For this, see our accompanying chapter in these proceedings. For $2f_2 - f_1$, there was a clear correlation between the DPs and DPOAEs, both were independent of f_2/f_1 . Regrettably region/location of $2f_2 - f_1$ DP generation always laid beyond (*i.e.*, more apical) our recording location, and we were unable to extract information about the cochlear extent (*re.* the stimulus tones) involved in this DPOAE's generation.

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COMMENTS AND DISCUSSION

[Lisa Olson]: You started your talk with a technical question. I'll start my questions going back to that. We, years ago, based on heterodyne interferometry we looked at interfering points. Heterodyne is a lot like OCT in the way that we extract the vibration. If you have two reflecting points you really want to be measuring from a peak [...] The effect of the peak is that you can get interference, which you can think of as a weighted average or something. But the effect can be much worse. If you have to things that move linearly you can have nonlinear effects. Anyway, we chose to measure from the peaks based on the [following] two articles (de la Rochefoucauld *et al.* (2005), doi: 10.1121/1.1848177; Lin *et al.* (2017), doi: 10.1121/1.4973867).

[Chris Bergevin]: It seems that you are plotting the data in an iso-level situation. Could you do an iso-response, in which you vary the level to see how things vary in that way, and maybe get phase information from that which maybe a little bit easier to relate back to the DPOAEs?

[Sebastiaan Meenderink]: Yes, in principle we could. In our system it takes a little bit of time to analyze the recordings, so an iterative recording process to change the stimuli to get iso-response would take a bit of time. But it is feasible. We did not do this in this case. I am not sure how this would make the relationship between the measured intracochlear DPs and the ear-canal DPOAEs easier. We record DPOAEs as iso-stimulus responses, similar to the reported DP data.

[Jont Allen]: Do you agree with the statement, or do I agree with your statement that the distortion product is mostly generated at the f_2 place? Because if it combines the L_1 and the L_2 , it's got to be where they are interacting. So all the DPs have to be generated at [near] the f_2 place and propagate back to the ear canal. Do you agree with that statement?

[Sebastiaan Meenderink]: I believe the statement should be a bit more nuanced, but [for ear-canal DPOAEs] the answer seems to be mostly yes [For intracochlear DP generation, the answer is no. Many of these DPs, once generation, do not seem to contribute to the DPOAE. Apparently, they are unable to propagate back to the ear canal. See also Bowling *et al* (2021), doi: 10.1038/s41598-021-93099-7]. One of the questions that came up is based on the observation in OCT data that the responses in the outer-hair cell region as much less tuned than those on the BM: they show a substantial response in the low frequency tails as well. With this, the L_1 , L_2 overlap region could potentially extend to locations that are basal from the f_2 tonotopic site, and ...

[Jont Allen]: ... not if there is a second filter. So, I did this experiment many years ago and I looked for the location on the basilar membrane where the signal [ear-canal DPOAE] was coming from, looking for a power generation. The experiment did not find it. It was repeated by at least three other people and they [also] did not find any amplification on the way back to the ear canal, or on the way in. It is a big effect, because it is twice the gain of the cochlear amplifier. And I just want to make sure your data is in agreement with this, or not. If it does not, I think I am gonna leave the field.

[Sebastiaan Meenderink]: Our data does not say anything about the presence, absence or existence of cochlear amplification. We just looked to see whether there were distortion products in the measured responses. There were, but I don't know whether they were amplified. The research question was just: Can we figure out what region of the cochlea, the tonotopic locations relative to the stimulus, is responsible for generating DPOAEs. Is it just the f_2 -place? Is it extending basally? And it turns out to be harder than we hoped for.

[James Dewey]: The normalization to the expected local DP phase and amplitude is an interesting approach. I wonder, however, if "local" DPs can be assumed to follow the theoretically expected phase and amplitude behaviors throughout the organ of Corti or only near the actual nonlinear source (*i.e.*, the OHCs). For this reason, I might question whether deviations from expected phase or amplitude behavior at the level of the BM (or elsewhere) necessarily indicate the presence of propagating DPs. These differences could reflect some other transformation of locally OHC-generated force to BM motion, for example.

[Sebastiaan Meenderink]: Our interpretation in terms of "local" and "non-local" components is based on the presence of a slope in the phase-vs-frequency curves. If this group delay is non-zero, we take it to indicate there is some propagation time between the locus of DP genesis and the recording site. It is possible to get a non-zero slope that is not associated with propagation if the (phase of the) transfer function (*e.g.*, from OHC to BM) varies with frequency. In our data, the phase relation between BM and OHC responses to the stimulus tones shows little dependence on frequency, certainly not enough to explain the varying slopes in the DP phase-vs-frequency curves (*e.g.*, Fig. 4).

[James Dewey]: When referenced to the phase of the stimuli in the ear canal, a negative or positive sloping [DPOAE] phase[-vs-frequency] typically indicates forward or reverse traveling waves, respectively. Is this relationship somehow inverted when normalizing to the local stimulus response phases? [See Fig. 4 in manuscript.]

[Sebastiaan Meenderink]: For each DP, its phase is given relative to the phases of the stimulus tones recorded at the same recording location/OCT pixel. This means that the slope of their phase-vs-frequency curves provide information about the delay of the DP *re.* these stimulus tones. A negative (positive) slope indicates that the DP occurs after (before) the response to the stimulus at that OCT pixel. By itself, the slopes thus do not indicate direction of propagation, only that there is some delay between its generation and recording. The interpretation of these slopes as propagation direction requires some (reasonable?) assumptions on DP generation. For example, the phase-vs-frequency curves for BM $2f_1 - f_2$ responses have positive slopes for $f_2 > 3$ kHz (Fig 4b). Here, the assumption is that the $2f_1 - f_2$ DP is generated more basally (at the 3-kHz tonotopic site) *re.* the recording site (2-kHz). After its basal generation, the DP propagates (forward) to the recording site faster than the stimulus tones (because it has a lower frequency), resulting in the negative group delay.

[Samiya Alkhairy]: The phases (bottom panels) of the frequency response curves of figure 11b and 1c look unlike any I have seen before. Why does the phase switch to having a positive slope (around 3 kHz)? In the main text, I believe you only describe the phase up to the BF. But what's happening above BF is quite interesting (and odd) - I do wonder if what's behind this affects your later interpretations given two tones.

[Sebastiaan Meenderink]: The recorded phase responses were first referenced to the middle-ear (umbo) response. After that, we removed an additional delay of 0.5 ms. This was done so that the level-dependence of the phase responses became more discernible in the plot. The negative slope of the resulting phase-vs-frequency curves (for $f > 3$ kHz) indicates that it takes these frequency components less than 0.5 ms to propagate from the middle ear to the intracochlear recording location. See Figs 2c,d in Meenderink *et al* (2022), doi: 10.1038/s42003-022-04234-7 for phase-vs-frequency curves in which this additional 0.5 ms was not removed.

[Samiya Alkhairy]: Using your OCT set-up, what components of motion are you primarily picking up?

[Sebastiaan Meenderink]: The motion measured by the OCT system is along its measurement beam. This beam direction was vertical in the B-scan of Fig. 1a (which is the typical organ of Corti orientation we use during recordings). For motion that is not parallel to this direction, the OCT system measures the projection of this motion onto its beam (i.e. the measured motion is a scaled version of the "true" motion, where the scaling factor is given by $\cos(\alpha)$, with α the angle between the true motion direction and the OCT beam). It is thus possible (and very likely) that the responses we report are (projections of) motions that are not parallel to the OCT beam, for example vibrations in the transverse, radial, and longitudinal directions of the cochlea.